

Royal Society: culture award application 2024

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1. Why should the candidate be considered for this medal?

I am nominating The Turing Way (TTW) team for the culture award, acknowledging their significant contributions to democratising access to data science skills and transforming global research culture. TTW, an open science and community-led project at The Alan Turing Institute, is renowned for its high-quality data science handbook. Co-created by a global community, the handbook includes over 350 chapters across five guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration, and Ethical Research, covering topics from sharing code and data to managing reproducible workflows and building diverse teams. TTW emphasises an inclusive research culture, aiming to enable participatory co-creation, fair incentives, recognition, and respectful collaboration at all research stages. The Guide to Research Ethics incorporates key principles from Responsible Research and Innovation and Research Integrity while addressing activism, environmental sustainability, and internal policy advocacy.

TTW is dedicated to embedding open, reproducible, and collaborative practices across sectors using data science. Tailored training materials and community documentation provide comprehensive information for all stakeholders, ensuring best practices from conception to conclusion throughout the research lifecycle. TTW's strength lies in its diverse international community of practitioners committed to building an equitable, kind, and collaborative research culture, aiming to reduce harm and enhance benefits, especially for vulnerable and marginalised communities.

Notable collaborator-led impact include the Office for National Statistics' resources inspired by TTW to promote internal best practices in government, NASA's Transform to Open Science program, creating a nationally supported 'open science hi 101' curriculum training 20,000 learners in 2024 and the eScience Center Netherlands research engineering team sharing and maintaining their practice-based resources on TTW. In 2023, TTW launched the BridgeAI-funded TTW Practitioners Hub to collaborate with UK organisations to promote open and responsible AI adoption; conducted research on diversifying research and data science roles, and delivered talks and workshops in 70 international conferences.

Significantly, the TTW team hasn't achieved these by working with a select group of people who decide what "best practices" look like in different contexts. Instead, their collaborative approaches have empowered over 470 diverse individuals from various backgrounds, identities, and lived experiences to express their viewpoints, represent different realities in research and amplify voices from traditionally marginalised communities in STEM. They have provided a working example of team science, defining standards, practices, and pathways for conducting responsible research across sectors such as academia, industry, government, and public sectors, and fields including engineering, humanities, and science.

Over the past 5 years, the project has grown to support multiple initiatives, community-driven working groups, and skill-building activities. The project's governance structure includes three levels: community contributors, self-organised maintainer working groups, and constitutional-level community representations alongside co-leads Malvika Sharan and Kirstie Whitaker. Community-led maintainer groups and core contributors oversee various aspects of the project, including accessibility, translation, localization, technical infrastructure, and collaborative events. These groups collaborate closely with dedicated staff at the Turing Institute: a Research Community Manager (Anne Lee Steele), a Research Project Manager (Alexandra Araujo Alvarez), a Senior Researcher (Malvika Sharan) and the Programme Director for Tools, Practices and Systems (Kirstie Whitaker).

2. List of key achievements

Since its 2019 launch, The Turing Way has not just advocated for transparency and equity, diversity, inclusion, and accessibility (EDIA) in data science but embraced them throughout their work, positively influencing research culture at the Alan Turing Institute and collaborating with national and international organisations. Nationally, TTW is at the forefront of a shift in how data science is done, influencing [UK government strategy on reproducibility in data analysis](#) and informing the [Health Foundation's](#) adoption of open practices. TTW was referenced in the Mayor of London's [Emerging Technology Charter](#), the [Goldacre Review commissioned by the Secretary of State for Health and Care](#) and the Innovation Scholars funding call by [UKRI](#). The handbook and community model have inspired similar resources, including the [Quality Assurance of Code for Analysis and Research](#) by the Office for National Statistics, [FAIR Cookbook](#) for the life sciences, and a [citizen science guide](#) for research libraries. It is also a key reference for a range of open science initiatives, like [Data Ethics Club](#) at university and [NASA's Transform to Open Science](#) at the national level.

As a flagship project, TTW assists researchers in embedding open science, reproducibility, and collaborative practices in data science and AI projects. It enables a bidirectional flow of information by providing a collaborative platform to share Institute practices broadly. Projects like [The Environmental Data Science Book](#), [Turing Data Stories](#) and [Turing Commons](#) utilise TTW's community model to establish and maintain public resources.

In 2022, TTW received OpenUK's Belonging in Research and Community Award and the 2021 HiddenRef Award for practices improving acknowledgement and incentives for hidden labour in research. With an author list boasting over 470 international contributors, including researchers, open science practitioners, educators and data experts across academia, government and industry, in various domains, at all levels of seniority. They have written 350+ subchapters and given over 200 talks and workshops globally covering topics such as open science, data management, research software, communication, collaboration, ethics and diversifying professions. Community members have also localised book chapters in languages including Arabic, Chinese, Portuguese, Spanish and Turkish. Web analytics show monthly engagement with 7,000 users, 17,000 page views, 35,000 resource downloads (from Zenodo), and 100+ citations to date. Users span multiple countries, including Australia, Argentina, Brazil, Germany, India, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Turkey, the UK, the USA, Venezuela, and beyond.

In 2023, the project launched the inaugural [Practitioner's Hub](#) cohort, engaging open research and open source experts across academia, research, engineering systems, government and healthcare, and sharing [case studies](#) with insights into the practical adoption of AI and data science. Subsequent cohorts, under the £100 million [BridgeAI initiative](#), will enable expert engagement across the AI landscape in the UK and beyond.

Starting in 2024, the team will work “Data Science Without Borders”, a consortium of African research institutes to assist the development and deployment of data science skills and AI tools in Ethiopia, Senegal and Cameroon in collaboration with the African Population and Health Research Center and Africa CDC.

3. Provide a brief summary of the Nominee’s career history

In 2018, The Alan Turing Institute – the UK’s National Institute for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (AI) – was awarded funding to undertake and apply data science and AI research that can transform the key areas of science, industry and government. TTW was founded by Dr Kirstie Whitaker who was a Research Fellow leading on reproducible approaches, one of the core requirements for translating research into cross-disciplinary innovation.

Since 2020, Dr Whitaker is the director of the Tools, Practices and Systems (TPS) Research Programme, one of the Institute’s Core Capabilities and representing cross-cutting initiatives which seek to build open source infrastructure with a decentralised network of people who connect data with domain experts. Co-lead investigator, Dr Malvika Sharan started as community manager of TTW in 2019. Since 2021 she is a Senior Researcher leading a team of Community Managers contributing toward building connections between research communities and supporting knowledge exchange.

TTW is a flagship project at The Alan Turing Institute. Managed by community manager, Anne Lee Steele and the project manager Alexandra Araujo Alvarez, all TPS members engage with TTW, serving as the bidirectional conduit of knowledge between different projects in Environment and Sustainability, AI for Science and Government, Data Centric Engineering, Research Software Engineering, and Health research. Community volunteers lead working groups relating to localisation and translation, infrastructure, community events and accessibility. Several team members represent organisational collaborations such as with eScience Centre Netherlands, TU Delft, VU Amsterdam, The Carpentries, MetaDocencia, 2i2c, Open Life Science and Open Science Saudi Arabia.

To foster a welcoming and supportive community, TTW embraced online working from the start. Since the book’s launch in 2019, the team has hosted regular events, including training workshops, remote co-working sessions, speaking engagements, mentored contribution sprints and project-specific consulting. TTW has been used worldwide, with over 7000 monthly visitors, nearly 1000 members engaging on the Slack workspace, 650 newsletter subscribers, and over 3500 followers of project updates on social media. An exemplar of inclusive remote working is the Book Dash event, which transitioned online in 2020 to ensure global participation, accommodating diverse time zones. The Turing provides accessibility support, covering aspects such as high-speed internet access, childcare grants, live transcription services, and subsistence costs for participants. This event design and support has enabled participants from African, Asian, European, Latin and North American countries to contribute.

The community’s commitment to inclusivity is further demonstrated through public, virtual “Fireside Chats”. These events convene experts and foster cross-community discussions on socio-technical themes, such as sustainability and open-source AI, drawing cumulative attendance from over 1000 participants. The Practitioners Hub “Experts in Residence” joined the community in 2023, supporting each other and advocating for best practices in industry, government and the third sector. Started in 2024, the community are hosting online calls to openly discuss and evolve governance structures in line with the community’s growth and expanding initiatives. Continuing onboarding and training activities will ensure that new members are equipped to engage effectively with the project and the broader data science landscape.

4. Please provide information on any other relevant achievements or awards held by the Nominee

Here are some notable achievements and awards held by the Nominee:

1. In 2021, TTW received a 'Highly Commended Project' award under the 'Practices' category from HiddenRef. HiddenRef is dedicated to gaining greater recognition for all research contributions, particularly those in traditionally overlooked roles within research infrastructure. Notably, community managers, research software engineers, data stewards, and others were acknowledged. To further advocate for diverse roles in data science and research, team members Emma Karoune and Malvika Sharan received a Skills Policy Award in 2023 by the Turing's Skills Team. This funding enabled them to conduct systematic research and producing reports that will be used for engaging with the policy landscape to professionalise data science roles nationally. The team collaborated with the TTW community and national stakeholders, contributing recommendations to institutional policies and supporting the Festival of the HiddenREF in 2023. These activities aimed to create a more effective and equitable research environment, bringing together professionals from often undervalued roles.

2. In 2022, The Turing Way team received the OpenUK award for Belonging. This recognition was awarded for their commitment to fostering a thriving and diverse community through collective efforts. The global impact of TTW is evident as various stakeholders, including ONS, the UK government analysis function, and NASA-TOPS, utilise it to inform ongoing research and advocate for the future direction of data science globally. Notably, the team behind NASA-TOPS collaborated with the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, contributing to the launch of the '2023 Year of Open Science' nationwide, involving influential national research organisations.

3. In 2022, TTW was nominated for the Royal Society Athena Prize, and received positive feedback despite not winning. The award panel praised the nomination as a strong combination of ethical science and inclusivity. They highlighted evidence of its use and adaptability, labelling it a good example of best practice with high transferability across different fields and as an extremely innovative and long-lasting initiative. This feedback reinforced the TTW team's commitment to establishing a dedicated forum to engage practitioners and experts openly, generating more evidence on how TTW is accelerating the adoption of open and responsible AI across different sectors, establishing itself as an important digital public good. In 2023, this effort led to the creation of Practitioner's Hub, funded by the Ecosystem Leadership Award from EPSCRC granted to the TTW team by the Alan Turing Institute and the InnovateUK BridgeAI project. The team collaborates with the Turing's Skills team, AI Standards Hub, Digital Catapult, and Hartree as delivery partners. A set of case studies shared from the first cohort highlight the "state of best practices" from the five participating organisations, showcasing their commitment to advancing best practices and participating in cross-sector collaboration.

5. Statement of support

Historically, research has often operated within isolated groups, perpetuating a model where a select few 'privileged' academics held sway. However, in a world where data-driven technologies permeate every aspect of our society, such a siloed approach is no longer sufficient. The Turing Way (TTW) emerges as a pioneering force, offering a blueprint for collaborative and inclusive data science. This is achieved through two key pillars: (1) providing a comprehensive handbook and (2) exemplifying the conduct of open, community-led projects in the development of its valuable resources.

By nominating TTW for the Culture Award, my intention is to advocate for the broader acknowledgment of the TTW community's global impact on positive research culture, spanning both the Global South and North. TTW's international researchers and contributors collaboratively strive for sustainable solutions, aiming to enhance the application of data science for the benefit of all societal

stakeholders while mitigating harm to marginalised groups. They achieve this by curating and co-creating approaches to enhance research quality and culture, actively supporting EDIA initiatives, and championing research ethics reform. Importantly, all these endeavours unfold transparently, challenging the disconnected and isolated nature of traditional academic research.

TTW's efficacy lies in engaging and empowering individuals and groups with diverse skills, backgrounds, lived experiences, and domain knowledge. The project is committed to responding to the community needs and interest, while evolving their own practices. Personal mentorship by project leads and core team members, coupled with training, leadership, and career development opportunities, underscore TTW's dedication to engaging and nurturing its community. To ensure inclusivity, resources, guidance, templates, and training are provided, enabling involvement of members irrespective of previous experience.

TTW employs a decentralised governance process, deliberately avoiding individual authorship in favor of establishing shared ownership and agency within the project. Acknowledgment of contributions is a priority, particularly recognising roles that involve hidden labour in research, often undertaken by members from marginalised communities in research and tech spaces. Notably, the TTW book is attributed to the community, with each contributor listed as an author.

The collaborative engagement of both Turing staff researchers and an international volunteer community empowers TTW to ensure the adoption and sustainability of its resources in the long term. Moreover, it enables others to reuse these resources to develop similar projects for specific audiences. TTW has already inspired researchers globally to reevaluate their practices, prioritising reproducibility and ethical considerations.

In light of recent government reports emphasising the need for change in research culture in the UK and globally, particularly in open science, I firmly believe that the Culture Award is a fitting recognition for TTW's pivotal role in fostering a transformative culture in data science. TTW is poised to continue empowering thousands of contributors to envision and contribute to a truly global research culture for the next generation.